

945358-BIGPICTURE
Central Repository for Digital Pathology

WP4 - Tools for accessing, annotating and mining digital slides

D4.07 - Report on integration and validation of QC algorithms and associated source code in the BIGPICTURE infrastructure

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Abstract

Data quality is one of the leading metrics determining the value of any public repository. Although manual data curation is the gold standard for ensuring quality, manual curation quickly becomes untenable when repository sizes approach thousands of images, let alone millions, as in the case of the Bigpicture repository. Additionally, the images included in the Bigpicture repository are not regular images but whole-slide images that are gigapixels in size and whose quality cannot be judged briefly but require careful inspection at high resolution, increasing the burden of manual curation.

This deliverable aims to investigate and develop an automated method for basic image quality control. Specifically, the most common cause of poor image quality in digitized histopathology is staining or scanning artifacts. We investigated existing approaches to (semi-)automatically identify artifacts in whole-slide images identifying best practices. Subsequently, we developed a Bigpicture artifact detection model using those best practices to identify use cases. A training set for model development containing artifact classes such as pen markers, out-of-focus regions, dust, and air bubbles, among others, was collected. The model was optimized using an internal validation set and subsequently validated on a diverse set of 500 whole-slide images from more than ten laboratories and across different tissues and stains. The model was evaluated using manual annotations on the pixel and slide levels. Performance was deemed adequate for integration in the Bigpicture infrastructure (average Dice coefficient is 0.83, with a slide-level accuracy of >90%, which will be further refined during the project's runtime).

In addition to the artifact detection model, we also investigated the possibility of generating realistic artifacts to validate QC algorithms, the results of which were subsequently scientifically published.

The code, data, and a web-accessible version of the model will all be published through the consortium GitHub and the Bigpicture platform to allow reuse and refinement. This allows slide contributors to run the model on their local infrastructure before submitting data to Bigpicture. In addition, we are currently planning to add the model to the data submission infrastructure as soon as the inference hardware is in place and operational.

Methods

Motivation and state-of-the-art

Data quality control is integral to ensuring the validity of results in academic research and industrial development. Image artifacts are a key component of image quality and cannot be corrected after data acquisition, unlike other sources of poor quality, such as colour or white balance. This is not unique to applications using digitized histopathology. Still, this area does come with its specific challenges, for example, the wide variety of sources causing artifacts, such as tissue preparation, staining, and digitization. Additionally, a single whole-slide image already contains gigapixels of data, prolonging inspection for even small artifacts. Several authors have shown that bad image quality and artifacts can deteriorate the quality of manual inspection and automated image analysis of digitized histopathology [Schömig-Markiefka et al. Mod Pathol (2021)].

To ensure that the Bigpicture repository contains high-quality data, a full manual inspection of every uploaded slide would be the gold standard. However, this would also be infeasible as it would entail domain experts going over 3 million digitized slides in detail. Instead, we have opted for a (semi-)automated approach that involves developing an algorithm to automate the most cumbersome QC task: identifying and assessing the extent of common image artifacts. There are two important sidenotes to this endeavour:

1) It is not our goal to make sure all data in the repository is completely artifact-free, as this would reduce the usefulness of the repository by not mirroring real-world data. The goal is to automatically flag slides that have such poor quality that they are effectively unusable.

2) We are not claiming that slides would be acceptable for a specific diagnostic or research question. For example, a single out-of-focus tile on top of a cluster of metastatic cells might be an unacceptable artifact for some use cases. In contrast, in other use cases, it would be fine if 20% of the slide is affected by artifacts.

At the start of the development of the Bigpicture artifact detection algorithm, we first surveyed the current state-of-the-art, which was and is relatively limited, especially with respect to automated approaches,

The most well-known and highest-cited QC algorithm for digitized histopathology is the HistoQC software package [Janowczyk et al. *JCO Clin Cancer Inform* (2019), Chen et al. *J Pathol* (2022)], which includes tools and a GUI for several types of artifacts, for example, air bubbles, out-of-focus regions, and pen markings. Although an excellent example of open-source software tested across different centres and tissue types, it lacks several common tissue artifacts, such as tissue folds, ink, and dust, to name a few. Additionally, it is still a highly involved manual process in which users must run and visualize different modules separately. Others have built on this initial effort, offering more automated tools. For example, Berman et al. [PLoSOne, (2023)] developed the SliDL package, a digital pathology machine learning library with a larger scope than just QC but including artifact segmentation. However, the package is not maintained, was only validated on 61 slides, and only offers a single ‘artifact’ class. Last, Haghghat et al. [Sci Rep, (2022)] offer another, similar solution in PathProfiler, which also includes an algorithm for artifact detection. Sadly, this algorithm was only trained and validated for a single use case, specifically assessing prostate biopsies. Last, none of these algorithms have been validated for toxicological pathology or immunohistochemically stained slides.

Figure 1: Examples of common image artifacts in digitized histopathology images

Other solutions exist for single types of artifacts, such as tissue folds; the current state-of-the-art lacks a fully automated algorithm that can assess the most common classes of artifacts, works across different tissue types and stains, and is validated on a large set of cases. In this deliverable, we set out to address these gaps.

Preliminary work

The first attempt to build an algorithm that addresses all the aforementioned gaps was made at Radboudumc in 2021. We decided to tackle the problem of artifact detection through semantic

segmentation, which allows us to localize and quantify the size of different artifacts. We settled on trying to identify the six most common artifact classes: out-of-focus, ink, markers, tissue folds, air bubbles, and dust (Figure 1). We collected a diverse set of 142 whole-slide images, consisting of 9 tissue and 8 stain types digitized using 7 scanners. We annotated 3278 artifacts exhaustively in one or more regions from each slide. Additionally, we collected 30 unannotated images from an external data centre to evaluate the performance of our approach, which we refer to as an external test set. The model was based on DeepLabV3+, a popular semantic segmentation framework in medical imaging, and we compared the method against HistoQC. The results are summarized in Figure 2 and were published at the MIDL scientific conference [Smit et al. *MIDL* (2021)].

Figure 2: Preliminary results for a DeepLabV3-based semantic segmentation algorithm for artifact detection. On the left side is a Table with the Dice coefficient for different categories of artifact; on the right, several qualitative examples, with the middle row showing the reference annotation and the bottom row the output of the algorithm.

Although these initial results were impressive, for the Bigpicture algorithm, we require more extensive validation and better support for different stains and tissue types. Specifically, in the Description of Action, we indicated that we wanted to validate across a test set of 500 slides, not just 30.

Investigation of an alternative patch-classification-based approach

As part of the Novartis Translational Medicine Data Science Academy Program, a fellow investigated the use of patch-based classification approaches on histopathology datasets for use in artifact detection (Haghighat et al. [Sci Rep, (2022)]). As a dataset for training and validation, 60 rat WSIs with liver and kidney sections were expertly annotated for artifacts such as dry tissue, tissue folds, floaters, extraneous objects, air bubbles, and out-of-focus. An expanded version of this dataset is provided to validate the algorithm developed in this report (see description below).

In this approach, tissue areas on a whole slide image were identified using Otsu's method, split into patches of size 224 x 224 pixels at a resolution of 1.008 microns per pixel, and labelled as normal tissue or containing artifacts. In cases where a patch contained more than one artifact, the class with the largest pixel area was used. Using this dataset, a ResNet18 network was trained to identify patches containing artifacts and predict the artifact class.

In evaluating the results, the network showed promising performance when considering the limited amount of labelled data available for certain artifact types. However, in qualitative comparisons with output from semantic segmentation models such as DeepLabV3+, the semantic segmentation approach showed similar performance while providing more fine-grained artifact data localization. Therefore, the decision was made to focus further development on semantic segmentation models instead of the patch-classification approach.

In addition to this work, patches with synthetic artifacts were also investigated at both Novartis and HES-SO. The results of HES-SO were more extensive and used part of the data collected for the Artifact Detection Method. As such it will be discussed fully further in this deliverable.

At Novartis, synthetic artifacts approximated tissue folds, out-of-focus, air bubbles, and extraneous objects were implemented. It was investigated if such synthetic artifacts enhanced the performance of the classification model above when added to the training dataset; however, it was observed that the accuracy of the classifier did not increase significantly with their use, and in general, it showed poor

generalization performance.

These results were presented as a poster at the Bigpicture Annual Meeting 2023. The poster, as well as the code used in creating the results, are available on request.

Development of Bigpicture Artifact Detection Model

Our preliminary work also involved assessing several neural network architectures for semantic segmentation, and the results are shown in [Smit et al. *MIDL* (2021)].

This resulted in an artifact detection model architecture based on DeepLabV3+, using an EfficientNet-B2 encoder pre-trained on ImageNet. A schematic representation of the model's architecture is provided in Figure 3. The model is configured with various hyperparameters, including dropout, loss function (Dice Loss), and optimizer (Adam). The training process involves multiple epochs across the training dataset, and the learning rate is scheduled using a cosine annealing scheduler. A comprehensive overview of these hyperparameters is presented in Table 1 for reference.

Figure 3: Architecture of the segmentation model with EfficientNetB2 encoder and DeepLabV3+ decoder.

Hyperparameter	Value
Encoder weights	ImageNet
Batch normalization	True
Pooling	Average
Dropout	0.4
Segmentation loss	Dice Loss
Segmentation loss weight	0.8
Classification loss	Cross Entropy
Classification loss weight	0.2
Learning rate	5.0e-4
Epochs	150
Batch size	32
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate scheduler	Cosine Annealing

Table 1: Hyperparameters configuration

Data and annotation acquisition

Development dataset

A comprehensive training dataset comprising 142 slides was initially collected for this project. This dataset was divided into training, validation, and internal testing sets, with 100 slides (70%) allocated for training and 21 each (15%) for validation and internal testing.

As the project progressed, 458 additional slides were collected to further validate the model's performance. We refer to this set as the external test set. Combined with the 42 slides used for initial validation and internal testing, 500 annotated slides were used for the total test set.

The initial set of 100 slides used for training featured a rich diversity, encompassing nine distinct tissue types and nine different stain types (HE, PAS, CK20, CD3, CD8, CK81, CKPAN, P53, and Ki67). The digitization process involved using seven scanners to capture the real-world heterogeneity in pathology labs. This diversity was essential for ensuring the algorithm's adaptability to various tissue characteristics and staining techniques.

A detailed breakdown of the number of training slides per tissue type is presented in Table 2:

Tissue Type	Number of Slides
bonemarrow	6
breast	33
colon	17
kidney	7
lymphoma	7
pancreas	6
prostate	14
ovary	7
miscellaneous	5

Table 2: Distribution of training data across tissue types

External test set – Radboudumc

Within Radboudumc, we collected 156 slides from our research archives (Table 3). Of these, 76 slides originate from cohorts (centers, scanners) that were also used in the training data but originated from different patients. The remaining 80 slides were added from cohorts not used in the training data. These 156 cases had similar diversity in originating centers, scanners, and staining compared to the original development data.

Tissue Type	Stain	Scanner	Number of Slides
bonemarrow	HE, PAS	3DHistech P1000	7
breast	HE, CD3, CD8, CD45RO	3DHistech Pannoramic 250 Flash II, Hamamatsu NanoZoomer-XR C12000-01, 3DHistech P250, Philips Ultrafast Scanner, Hamamatsu XR C12000, Hamamatsu NanoZoomer C9600-13	53
cervix	HE	3DHistech P1000	14
colon	HE, CD8, CK20	3DHistech Pannoramic 250 Flash II, 3DHistech P1000	31
kidney	HE, CD34, PAS		5
liver	HE, CD3, CD8	3DHistech P1000	15
lung	HE	3DHistech P1000	15
lymphoma	HE		5
ovary	HE	3DHistech P1000	2
pancreas	CD3, CK81 CKPAN, CD8	3DHistech Pannoramic 250 Flash II, 3DHistech P1000	30
prostate	HE	Leica Aperio AT2, Hamamatsu C9600-12, 3DHistech P1000	15
skin	HE	3DHistech P1000	4
miscellaneous	HE, Ki67	3DHistech P1000	2

Table 3: Description of Radboudumc test set

External test set - TCGA

Another common repository for developers of AI algorithms for digitized pathology is the Cancer Genome Archive (TCGA), containing data from over 13 contributing centers. We included 10 slides each of kidney and skin tissue. All these slides were stained with HE and digitized with varying Aperio scanner equipment.

External test set – Novartis

161 slides from Novartis were randomly selected from 7 rat dose-finding studies, stained with standard HE staining protocol, and scanned using Aperio AT2 and Aperio GT450 scanners. The slides contained 91 liver sections and 70 kidney sections.

External test set – Janssen

A total of 66 slides collected at Janssen during archive digitization were included. These slides were specifically selected for the presence of significant artifacts and to showcase different studies and tissues from dogs and rats. In Table 4, we highlight all the different organs on the slides. All slides were digitized with either a Leica Aperio GT450 or the Hamamatsu NanoZoomer XR.

Dog	Rat
Injection site, IV, saphenous vein	Lymph nodes, popliteal
Lymph nodes, axillary	Eye, nerve optic
Eye, nerve optic	Harderian gland
Trachea	Injection site, IM
Injection site, IV, cephalic vein	Brain
Brain, optic chiasma	Thymus

Gall bladder	Larynx
Esophagus	Bone, sternum
Bone, femur	Bone marrow, sternum
	Bone, femur
	Bone marrow, femur
	Spinal cord, cervical
	Spinal cord, thoracic
	Spinal cord, lumbar
	Heart, Artery, Aorta
	Kidney
	Spleen
	Lung
	Stomach; Small intestine, Duodenum
	Small intestine, Jejunum; Small intestine, Ileum; Peyer's Patches
	Gland, Thyroid; Gland, Parathyroid
	Uterus, Cervix, Vagina
	Stomach; Small intestine, Duodenum; Pancreas; Small intestine, Jejunum; Small intestine, Ileum; Peyer's Patches; Large intestine, Cecum; Large intestine, Colon; Large intestine, Rectum

Table 4: Overview of slides obtained from Janssen

External data - Bigpicture

Last, 55 slides were included from the Utrecht Medical Center and Linköping University Hospital submissions to the Bigpicture repository. These slides were specifically included because they follow the data submission format (DICOM) and standard common in Bigpicture. These slides all contain HE-stained tissue from varying organs encountered in clinical pathology, such as breast slides and skin tissue. Slides from Utrecht were digitized using a Hamamatsu XR scanner, whereas slides from Linköping were scanned with either a Hamamatsu S60, S360, XR, or XRL.

Pixel-level annotation process for the external test set

All slides except the Novartis cohort

The annotations for this project, excluding the Novartis dataset, were conducted by trained students. For each slide, specific Regions of Interest (ROIs) were initially selected, after which students exhaustively annotated the artifacts within each designated area.

Novartis

Following a guideline created by internal pathologists and scientists, one pathologist and two trained scientists annotated the slides. All observed artifacts in the tissue area were annotated, while artifacts in the white background were sparsely annotated. When artifacts' borders were unclear or too complex, general area annotation was made, including a variable amount of non-artifact area. The artifact classes annotated were tissue folds, dry tissue, air bubbles, scratched tissue, out-of-focus, and floaters. Subsequently, a peer review by an independent pathologist was performed to ensure consistency and accuracy of annotations.

Slide-level annotation process for the external test set

For slide-level assessments of quality, a pathology resident and algorithm developer scored each slide as poor or good quality, blinded to the output of the AI model.

Training and validation of Bigpicture Artifact Detection Model

Preprocessing

The preprocessing steps involved patch extraction from the WSIs. Patches are extracted with a size of 320x320 pixels without overlap. Patches are randomly sampled from annotated regions within the WSIs. Two distinct spacings, 2.0 and 4.0, are considered during the patch extraction process.

Figure 4: Examples of training patches with annotations and predictions

Patch extraction and training process

During training, the model processes batches of patches, learning to distinguish artifact patterns at both pixel and patch levels. We employ a dual-loss strategy, combining segmentation loss (Dice Loss) and patch-level classification loss (Cross-Entropy Loss). The segmentation task involves distinguishing artifact patterns at the pixel level, enabling precise localization and extent of areas containing potential artifacts. The classification task evaluates whether the artifacts within a given patch are predicted correctly. The segmentation loss is weighted with 0.8, while the classification loss is weighted with 0.2.

Inference and validation

We employ a two-step process in the inference stage to ensure accurate artifact detection. The first step involves leveraging a tissue segmentation network to preprocess the input whole-slide image. The tissue segmentation network eliminates white spaces surrounding the tissue block, providing a more focused input for artifact detection. Subsequently, we apply the trained artifact segmentation network to the pre-processed image, using patches of 1024×1024 pixels at a spatial resolution of $4.00 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ with 25% overlap. Test-time spatial augmentations, including 90° , 180° , and 270° rotations, and horizontal and vertical flips, are applied to enhance model robustness.

Our model's performance is evaluated using different metrics, including Dice Score for segmentation accuracy and Accuracy for patch-level classification. These metrics comprehensively assess the model's ability to detect and categorize artifacts. An example of patch-level inference results is shown in Figure 4.

Generation of artificial artifacts

We also investigated the potential to enhance WSI classification models by transferring realistic artifacts and augmenting existing datasets. Our method transfers artifacts onto new images, necessitating careful blending to minimize imperfections. We augment artifacts, ensuring alignment with source image staining and resolution or normalizing artifacts before overlaying them onto destination tissue.

Figure 5: The process of augmenting a WSI with an artifact from previously extracted artifact collection.

Our two-phase processing pipeline involves annotating and extracting artifacts from source images, employing a windowed approach due to the large size of WSIs. The constructed artifact library serves as a collection for sampling artifacts. In the second phase, we semi-randomly sample training examples using a segmentation model to determine insertion positions. We scale artifacts to the correct magnification level using spacing metadata, apply an affine transformation for shape modification, and align annotations on top of destination images. Images can be modified multiple times, with annotations appended to global masks.

For evaluation, we trained YOLOv5m for the detection network and ResNet50 for the classification network, using transfer learning methods with frozen model parts. Augmented images were cut into individual patches for batch training. A schematic overview of the pipeline is in Figure 5.

Results

Quantitative pixel-level results of the artifact segmentation network

The artifact segmentation network is evaluated at the pixel level within the annotated regions of interest. We evaluate pixel-level accuracy and the Dice coefficient at the levels of multi-class (seven different artifact classes) and binary (artifact vs. non-artifact). The results are presented in Table 5 and the confusion matrix in Figure 6.

Class	Dice coefficient
Folds	0.68
Ink	0.82
Bubbles	0.90
Dust	0.81
Marker / Pen	0.97
Out-of-focus	0.74
Artifact-free tissue	0.91

Table 5: Dice coefficient for different artifact classes

Figure 6: Pixel-level accuracies for different artifact classes presented in a confusion matrix

As can be seen, the model achieves a 94% accuracy in binary classification of artifact vs non-artifact tissues, achieving performance per the goals set out in the Description of the Action. An aspect for further development is the misclassification of different artifact types. This is often also caused by subjective interpretation of the original annotators. For example, tissue folds can cause out-of-focus regions around the fold, sometimes annotated as tissue folds. Another challenge around out-of-focus regions was that in the training data, most out-of-focus regions had a strong blurriness. In contrast, in the test data, most out-of-focus regions had a very slight, sometimes imperceivable blur. We aim to address this in the future using our artifact generation pipeline.

Another surprising mistake is the misclassification of air bubbles. This is mainly caused by the interior

of the air bubbles looking like normal tissue. The edges of the air bubble are classified with high accuracy. In a later phase, this issue might be resolved with a post-processing step such as hole-filling.

Qualitative pixel-level results

To better appreciate the output of the artifact segmentation model, we highlight several examples on the external test set in Figures 8 – 11.

Quantitative slide-level results

The model's performance is assessed at the slide level by examining the proportion of tissue covered by artifacts. Slides are categorized into two binary scores: 0 for poor quality and 1 for good quality. The percentage of artifacts is converted into a binary score based on a threshold; specifically, slides where the percentage of tissue containing more than 2.5% of artifacts is labelled poor quality. The chosen threshold is determined by carefully examining the slides to establish an accurate criterion for defining quality. Additionally, ink artifacts have been excluded from the computation as they generally do not impact pathologists' evaluation, but these are important for AI algorithms' analysis. The quantitative results are represented in Figure 7 and Table 6.

Metric	Score
Accuracy	0.95
F1 score	0.97
AUC	0.95

Table 6: Slide-level metrics for assessing artifacts

Figure 7: Confusion matrix that illustrates the model's performance in distinguishing between poor and good quality slides.

Qualitative slide-level results

Figure 8: Example of an HE tissues with extensive air bubbles. The orange and green rectangles highlight ROIs in which the model was validated. The annotation of the different artifact classes can also be seen in the ROIs

Figure 9: Example of HE slide completely out of focus. The model accurately segments all the out of focus tissue.

Figure 10: Example of an Immunohistochemically stained slide showing extensive tissue folds. Here it is good to see that the model is not confused by the dark brown stained immune cells.

Figure 11: A relatively high-quality slide where the model has correctly identified and highlighted several speckles of dust.

Overall, the qualitative picture level results approach the quality of the annotations performed by the manual annotators, and in many cases, it is ambiguous which resultant segmentation is more accurate.

Processing time and hardware requirements

The model was trained and evaluated using a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti GPU. The training spanned 150 epochs, employing a batch size of 32, with each epoch taking approximately 1 hour, including training and validation steps. During inference, the model processes each slide image (WSI) on the same GPU in approximately two minutes on average.

Planned integration in Bigpicture Data Submission Pipeline

Although not formally part of this deliverable, the overall goal within the project is to add the developed algorithm to the data submission pipeline of the Bigpicture repository. This will be achieved in two ways: locally and on-platform. A schematic overview is shown in Figure 12. Local application of the algorithm is facilitated through a downloadable Docker container that applies the algorithm to any set of images and produces a report and segmentation maps. The user can decide how these will be interpreted and visualized.

Figure 12: Flowchart of proposed integration of artifact detection algorithm in Bigpicture submission process.

The on-platform option is more essential, as this will be integral to ensuring repository data quality. The same Docker container for local use will be applied to every uploaded image before it is formally added to the repository. The data submitter will subsequently receive a report of all uploaded cases, sorted by the percentage of tissue area affected by artifacts. Suppose more than 10% of the tissue is affected. A manual inspection of the slide and the detected artifacts through Cytomine, the viewer front-end of the Bigpicture infrastructure, is mandatory before a slide can be committed. If submitters identify mistakes in the model output, these can be flagged. Other slides can also be inspected, but this

step is optional for these slides. For this integration to be completed, the AI inference hardware must be operational, which is expected to happen in 2024.

In addition to the integration of this version, periodically, the model will be retrained using the flagged model mistakes indicated by the data submitters. This allows the model to further improve over time.

Public release of code, algorithm, and data

In addition to integrating the algorithm in the Bigpicture repository, we will publicly release the source code via the imi-bigpicture GitHub organization (www.github.com/imi-bigpicture) to train and infer the algorithm. This will be released under the Apache v2.0 license. Additionally, the model encapsulated in a Docker container will be made available via the Harbor instance hosted by Bigpicture, both for download and running on the repository. The model weights will also be made available under a CC-BY license. Last, the model development and validation data will be uploaded to the Bigpicture infrastructure and publicly available under a CC-BY license.

Artifact generation results

Augmenting datasets with artificially generated artifacts substantially enhanced the performance of artifact detection networks, with an approximately 0.05 improvement in mean average precision and a noteworthy 0.14 increase in recall. In the classification task, improvements varied based on artifact type, including increasing AUROC values by 0.09. ROC curves are shown in Figure 13.

Monitoring loss charts showcased the system's proficiency in reducing overfitting, demonstrating consistent overall loss reduction and prevention of escalation throughout training (Figure 14).

Figure 13. ROC Curve for classification models, evaluated on Radboud University test annotations comprising of evenly sampled 70% of all dataset annotations – a) without, b) with the proposed augmentation. Model training was limited to only the last fully connected layer.

Figure 14: Chart of the validation loss during training.

The augmentation pipeline, blending annotated artifacts into the destination, proved utility in artifact detection, extending QC to real-world histology data despite limited training annotations. Our approach excelled in handling underrepresented or heterogeneous artifacts, showing significant improvements for artifacts like bubbles and dust. While effective in handling tissue artifacts in similar datasets, challenges arose with a complete mix of datasets and ink artifacts. Future research could address these challenges and explore improvements in stain transfer methods using recent advances in generative deep learning techniques.

Conclusion

We set out to develop an automated QC algorithm specifically for identifying artifact presence and extent in whole-slide images. In accordance with the description in the DoA, we validated the algorithm on 500 whole-slide images with a diversity of artifacts, sources, scanners, and even species. The KPIs that were defined for accepting the quality of the model were achieved, and the model is accurate enough for its purpose. Specifically, it achieved a slide level AUC of 0.95, which means it is reliable enough for pre-screening slides for artifacts. Integration within the platform is scheduled for 2024. As indicated, the intent is to improve the algorithm based on the submitted slides continuously. Contributors can flag mistakes in the algorithm, which will in turn be used to retrain the model. Additionally, we will set out to address the remaining weaknesses of the algorithm, such as subtle out-of-focus regions.

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